

Instructions for accessing the content of the workshop

Modern Predictive Microbiology Analysis in R

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A workshop presented on 27/28 June 2022 as part of the EFSA ListeriaPredict Project

Detailed course materials can be found in the online book - Handbook of Predictive Microbiology Growth Models Using R, Ursula Gonzales-Barron and Vasco Cadavez, available from:

<http://www.ipb.pt/~vcadavez/predmicro/>